

End-User Performance Isolation at Scale in Access Aggregation Networks

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Abstract—As broadband access speeds rise, the Access-Aggregation Network (AAN) faces growing challenges in ensuring scalable, fair, and predictable resource allocation for millions of subscribers. Traditional fairness mechanisms like Fair Queueing struggle to meet the scalability demands of modern AANs, constrained by hardware limitations and the complexity of managing per-user states at high speeds. Emerging programmable data plane technologies like P4 enables non-traditional QoS and resource sharing solutions. Core-Stateless Active Queue Management (CSAQM) is a recent proposal leveraging edge-based packet marking to enable fine-grained resource sharing while maintaining simplicity in core network schedulers.

In this paper, we present a scalable packet marking algorithm for CSAQM, implemented directly on a Tofino ASIC using P4 programming language. Our approach enables efficient, real-time marking of packets at line rate, supporting over one million users on a single switch. We detail the algorithm design and evaluate its performance in a high-speed testbed, simulating fair queueing for thousands of users on a 100 Gbps bottleneck. The results demonstrate that the proposed marker achieves significant scalability and performance, enabling resource allocation at scale in broadband networks.

Index Terms—Resource sharing, utility function, core-stateless AQM, packet marking, P4.

I. INTRODUCTION

As broadband access speeds continue to grow across both mobile and fixed networks, the Access-Aggregation Network (AAN) poses new scalability and performance challenges. The AAN serves as the intermediate layer between end-user access and core network infrastructure, aggregating traffic from thousands to millions of subscribers. While advances in access technologies (e.g., FTTH, 5G, and high-speed DSL) have dramatically increased last-mile bandwidth, they have also shifted performance bottlenecks toward the aggregation layer. Without efficient mechanisms for scalability and performance isolation, these bottlenecks risk undermining the potential benefits of modern broadband deployments.

When high-speed aggregation links are shared among a large population of users, the absence of proper performance isolation can lead to severe contention for bandwidth, particularly during peak periods. In such environments, resource allocation depends heavily on the number of active flows and the congestion control algorithms employed by each subscriber’s end systems. Traditional Quality of Service (QoS) mechanisms (e.g., per-flow scheduling, weighted fair queueing) can, in

principle, enforce fairness and traffic differentiation. However, their complexity and stateful nature make them difficult to scale in modern AAN environments, where maintaining per-subscriber or per-flow state would require excessive memory and processing resources in hardware. As a result, operators often resort to coarse-grained traffic management policies that trade precision for scalability. This limitation leads to unpredictable and unfair bandwidth distribution, where aggressive flows dominate available capacity while others experience degraded quality of experience. The problem is particularly detrimental for latency-sensitive applications such as video streaming, online gaming, and real-time communication, which demand predictable throughput and minimal jitter.

To address these challenges, programmable data planes offer unprecedented flexibility and scalability in implementing fine-grained traffic control mechanisms directly in the network hardware. By allowing network operators to customize packet processing behavior, programmable switches can dynamically adapt to changing traffic patterns and policy objectives. Recent studies have demonstrated the feasibility of implementing core-stateless resource sharing on P4-programmable devices [1], [2]. In core-stateless approaches, the resource sharing policy is implemented by a packet marker component that assigns a rank or a value to each packet of the users. At the bottleneck, the packet scheduler solely uses the packet markings to decide which packet to drop or forward in case of congestion. In the current implementations, the packet marking component has so far been realized only in software, limiting its scalability and integration with data plane scheduling functions.

In this paper, we propose a scalable, data plane-based packet marker design for the core-stateless resource sharing scheduler called CSAQM, specifically implemented for the Tofino ASIC. In this paper, we propose and evaluate a fully data plane-based packet marker for the CSAQM scheduler, implemented on the Intel Tofino ASIC. Building upon our earlier demonstration of its feasibility [3], we now provide a comprehensive design description, implementation details, and an extensive evaluation of its scalability and performance. Specifically, we demonstrate that our P4-based packet marker can emulate fair queueing behavior for up to 35,000 users on a 100 Gbps bottleneck link, and can be further scaled to emulate 195,000 users on a 90 Gbps link within a single Tofino switch. Finally, we also show that the packet marker running

on a single Tofino switch has the potential to support over one million users at line rate, indicating a substantial step towards highly scalable and fair resource allocation within the AAN.

II. RELATED WORK

Traditional fairness mechanisms, such as Fair Queueing (FQ) scheduling [4], are theoretically capable of enforcing equal (or weighted) resource distribution across users. However, these methods struggle to scale effectively as the number of subscribers grows, due to the impracticality of maintaining large number of queues, and processing flows individually. Implementing weighted fairness for 1 million users is challenging due to many factors: 1) it requires resource constraints on network hardware, such as limited memory and processing power, which makes it difficult to track and manage per-user state at high speeds. 2) Ensuring fair queueing requires many queues or complex scheduling algorithms that do not scale well, especially as traffic demands shift dynamically and require real-time adjustments. 3) These fairness mechanisms may increase latency and computational load, which can disrupt high-throughput, low-latency applications. Solutions often involve trade-offs, like grouping users or using approximate methods, to balance scalability with practical performance.

Emerging traffic management techniques, such as Hierarchical Core-Stateless Fair Queueing (HCSFQ) [5] and Core-Stateless Active Queue Management (CSAQM) [6], leverage advances in programmable data plane technology to enhance scalability and adaptability in traffic management. In the case of CSAQM, a Packet Value (PV) is assigned to each packet at the network edge, which then serves as an incentive for network nodes to prioritize, drop, or mark packets with Explicit Congestion Notification (ECN) based on predefined policies. This approach not only enables fine-grained control over resource allocation but also allows for rapid deployment of new policies by simply adjusting packet marking strategies at the network edge, leaving core schedulers unchanged.

III. CORE-STATELESS RESOURCE SHARING

The proposed method relies on the core-stateless resource sharing method called Per Packet Value (PPV). Similarly to other core-stateless proposals, the PPV framework consists of two key elements: 1) a packet marker which assigns values to each packet of a user (or more generally a traffic aggregate) according to a predefined resource sharing policy; and 2) a scheduler and Active Queue Management (AQM), which uses the values carried by packets to decide whether to drop a packet or mark it with ECN Congestion Encountered (CE) flag if the buffer is getting full.

Each user (or traffic aggregate) is assigned a unique, stateful packet marker instance, which labels incoming packets with a priority level known as the Packet Value (PV). This marking process is stateful because it depends on the user's throughput and the specific resource-sharing policy defined by a policy function called Throughput-Value Function (TVF). Each packet marker operates independently of other markers, network topology, and current network conditions.

The scheduler is deployed at each node (e.g., routers, end-hosts) within the PPV domain, as any node can potentially become a bottleneck. During periods of congestion, these nodes prioritize packets by PV, dropping or marking packets with the smallest PVs first, rather than using traditional methods like dropping the last packet or dropping uniformly at random. Several studies, including [1], [2], have demonstrated efficient algorithms and implementations of this PV-based scheduling on P4-programmable hardware.

An essential part of implementing the framework is to tag packets with PVs, using a Throughput-Value Function (TVF), which is derived from a utility function: $V_a(x) = U'_a(x)$. The utility function expresses the relationship between the allocated throughput and the user's satisfaction. For each user a , the utility function $U_a(x)$ represents the benefit (or value) that the user gains by allocating a throughput x to it. The derivative of the utility function represents the extra value (e.g., the increase in the user's satisfaction) gained by providing an extra unit of throughput to the user. In the Core-Stateless Resource Sharing framework, the packet marker tags packets such that each PV represents the marginal utility (i.e., value realized) if the packet is successfully delivered. For any user a with a sending rate R_a , the TVF $V_a(\cdot)$ defines a PV distribution such that packets with PV at least $V(x)$ contribute a throughput of x (for any $0 \leq x \leq R_a$).

Practically, the packet marker for each user measures the sending rate R_a , selects a rate x uniformly from the range $[0, R]$ when a packet arrives, and assigns a PV $p = V_a(x)$ to the packet. This results in a distribution of PVs for each user's traffic, enabling differentiated treatment in the network.

Fig. 1 illustrates how the TVFs and PVs can be used to share the bottleneck capacity between various users. In the first case, the bottleneck capacity is 10 Mbps shared between three user flows. The red, blue and green curves on the right side represent the TVFs of Flow1, Flow2 and Flow3, resp. The gray dotted line illustrates the cutoff value that results in a resource allocation 0, 6.25 and 3.75 Mbps for Flow1, Flow2 and Flow3, resp. This allocation is ensured by only transmitting packets with PV above the cutoff level. One can observe that Flow1 has no packet with PV above this threshold and thus it cannot even transmit a single packet. In the case of a 45Mbps bottleneck, the cutoff value is much smaller and thus all three flows have non-zero assigned throughput. The purple dotted line represents the cutoff value, leading to 10, 17.5 and 17.5Mbps throughput allocation for Flow1, Flow2 and Flow3, resp. In this case, packets below the threshold marked by the purple line are only dropped (or marked with ECN CE).

IV. DATA PLANE DESIGN FOR SCALABLE PACKET MARKING

In the PPV method, a dedicated packet marker instance plays a crucial role in realizing the resource-sharing policy for a given traffic aggregate. Each marker continuously monitors the arrival rate R_u of user u , selects a random sample uniformly between 0 and R_u and applies the user's TVF $v_u(\cdot)$ at this sampled value to determine the packet value for tagging

Fig. 1. The Throughput-Value Function (TVF)

the packet [6]. Although conceptually straightforward, implementing this mechanism on a P4-programmable ASIC like Tofino introduces challenges due to hardware constraints. For example, Tofino does not natively support floating-point arithmetic, cannot generate random numbers in arbitrary integer ranges, and imposes restrictions on multiplication operations. To overcome these limitations, we developed a streamlined packet marking algorithm specifically tailored to the Tofino ASIC, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

The packet processing pipeline begins with a user classification step implemented by the SubscriberRate table. This table matches each packet based on a subscriber identifier (e.g., IPv4/IPv6 address) and then executes an action that updates the corresponding rate measurement R and assigns the appropriate resource-sharing policy identifier for the user's traffic. The arrival rate for each user is calculated by updating a dedicated low-pass filter object with the packet size in Tofino's data plane.

Due to the lack of support for direct multiplication of arbitrary variables, we employ a logarithmic transformation: taking the logarithm of both variables and summing them. Similarly to prior studies [1], [2], we assume the TVF policy function exhibits exponential decay. This assumption allows us to use exponential binning of the throughput axis, yielding a discretized representation of the TVF. As shown in the figure, bin sizes are equidistant on a logarithmic scale. The bin Δ_i represents the throughput range from a^{i-1} to a^i for a predefined base value $1 < a < 2$. This table is precomputed, ensuring the upper bound of the final bin accommodates the maximum possible per-user rate. In our implementation, we use 1024 bins. To store the packet value in a finite number of bits, each bin Δ_i is mapped to a discrete packet value level ($v(a^i)$), represented by red lines in the figure.

To enable this compact representation, we first map the measured rate R to a bin index i , using the RateIndex table. This table applies range matching on the user's rate R and returns i such that $R \in \Delta_i$. Since the ASIC can only generate random values within the range $[0, 2^n - 1]$ (for bit-width $n \geq 1$), we take a random value rnd from range 0 to 255 and then compute the logarithm of $\frac{rnd}{255} \times R$. The RandomRateEstim table implements this logarithmic transformation and adjusts the bin index i accordingly, yielding a randomized index $rndbin$. As

Fig. 2. Data Plane Design of Packet Marking

the logarithm of the random value is negative, its complement ($y(x)$) is computed and stored in the table. Overflow-protected subtraction, denoted as $|-|$ in the figure, ensures the correct bin index is determined during table execution. The offset denoted by $y(x)$ is precomputed and embedded in the table.

Finally, the packet value for tagging is determined by applying the PolicyFunction table, which stores the discretized representations of various policy functions. The proposed design is efficient in terms of per-subscriber stateful resources on the data plane which is discussed in Section VI in more details.

In designing the packet marker's data plane, we considered typical policy functions and packet value (PV) encoding schemas. Aside from minor differences in rate measurement algorithms, the P4 pipeline in this implementation is functionally equivalent to the software-based packet marker implementations.

To explain the PV calculation, we present the following example. Let the maximum rate (R_{max}) be 100 Gbps (100,000 Mbps). First, we calculate $a = \sqrt[n]{R_{max}}$ which equals approximately 1.0113 when the number of bins is $n = 1024$. Using this value, we populate the RateIndex table, where each entry corresponds to the range $[a^{i-1}, a^i)$: for example, 0 - 1.0113 ($i = 0$), 1.0113-1.0227 ($i = 1$), ..., 14.999-15.169 ($i = 242$), and so on. After that consider a packet from a subscriber whose current rate (R) has been updated to 15 Mbps. We look up this rate in the RateIndex table and find the corresponding index $i = 242$. Then we generate a random number (rnd) between 0 and 255. Let's examine the extreme cases of rnd to compute $rndbin = i - y(rnd)$. For $rnd = 0$, the complement $y(0) = 1023$. Thus, $rndbin = 242 - 1023$. Since this

Fig. 3. Testbed setup for evaluation

is negative, the overflow-protected subtraction operator ($|-\rangle$) ensures $rndbin = 0$. For $rnd = 1$, $y(1) = -\log_{1.0113}(1/255)$. Substituting, $rndbin = 242 - (-\log_{1.0113}(1/255)) = -251$. Again, this is negative, so $rndbin = 0$. For $rnd = 255$, $rndbin = 242 - (-\log_{1.0113}(255/255)) = 242$ which equals i which is the rate index of R .

In this example, $rndbin$ ranges between 0 and $i = 242$. Finally, we use $rndbin$ and the corresponding policyID to look up the PV value in the PolicyFunction table. This table is pre-filled with PV values calculated for each $rndbin$. The value a^{rndbin} represents a random rate, which in this case lies between 0 Mbps and 15 Mbps. Applying the $v(\cdot)$ function to this random rate yields the final PV value. The introduced mechanism is simple and can be executed on a constrained data plane hardware like an Intel Tofino ASIC.

V. EVALUATION

Our evaluation setup is depicted in Fig. 3. The setup includes four servers, represented as yellow boxes, which act as traffic sources and sinks. A single Tofino switch (more precisely Tofino-1 with TNA architecture) is utilized to perform both packet marking and CSAQM scheduling. Since our testbed includes only one Tofino switch, the two data plane pipelines are co-located on the same device. A 100 Gbps bottleneck link is created by interconnecting the Tofino switch with a non-programmable switch, and this bottleneck is managed by the CSAQM scheduler.

Thousands of UDP flows, simulating subscriber traffic, are generated using the DPDK PktGen tool on TrafficGen-2, which connects to the Tofino switch via two 100 Gbps links. The throughput of these flows is monitored using a DPDK-based collector program running on TrafficSink-2, connected via a single 100 Gbps link. The other source and sink machines, TrafficGen-1 and TrafficSink-1, run iperf2 [7] to generate traffic for designated subscribers, with each connected via a 40 Gbps link.

Measurements are collected from both sink nodes and the P4 switch. Each user is assigned either a Silver or Gold policy, configured to achieve a throughput sharing ratio of 1:3.4 between Silver and Gold users, respectively. The evaluation was conducted under various scenarios, as described below. The scenarios are only static, showing cases with a fixed number of users. The dynamic case is not relevant for the marker, because each user has their own marker. The dynamic case is important for the scheduler, but this has already been analyzed in previous articles [6].

Fig. 4. 2,000 Gold UDP, 8,000 Silver UDP and 2 designated Gold UDP flows with 15 Mbps and 50 Mbps sending rate.

A. Designated users with different demands

Fig. 4 illustrates a scenario with 8,000 Silver users, 2,000 Gold users, and two designated Gold UDP flows (representing two designated users). The traffic for Silver and Gold users is generated by two separate interfaces of the machine TrafficGen-2, with Silver users on one interface and Gold users on the other. This setup produces a total load of 200 Gbps on the bottleneck link.

The applied policies yield average per-user throughputs of 21.8 Mbps and 6.4 Mbps for the Gold and Silver classes, respectively. It is depicted on the top subfigure. The throughput variation is insignificant. The designated users, governed by the Gold policy, generate traffic from TrafficGen-1. One flow transmits at 15 Mbps, starting at 24 seconds (denoted as t_1), while the other begins at 50 seconds (t_2) and transmits at 50 Mbps.

The bottom subfigure depicts the loss rates experienced by the two designated users. The first user, with a sending rate below its fair share of 21.8 Mbps, incurs no packet loss. In contrast, the second user, transmitting at a rate higher than its fair share (50 Mbps), experiences a 58% loss. Notably, despite the high loss, the second user achieves the same throughput as other Gold users.

This scenario demonstrates the resource-sharing behavior of our packet marker and scheduler under conditions of high but stable traffic loads. It highlights that users demanding less than their fair share remain unaffected by the high loss rates of other subscribers. Different users may experience very different packet losses at the bottleneck.

B. Designated users with congestion controlled flows

Fig. 5 illustrates the second scenario, where 10 Gold Cubic TCP flows are added to the system between TrafficGen-1 and TrafficSink-1. These flows emulate 10 additional users with congestion-controlled traffic, achieving a throughput of approximately 18.5 Mbps each, slightly below the UDP-based throughput of other Gold users. The packet loss rate for these TCP flows is about 2%.

Fig. 5. 2,000 Gold UDP, 8,000 Silver UDP, 2 designated Gold UDP flows with 15 Mbps and 50 Mbps sending rate and 10 Gold Cubic TCP flows

This scenario highlights that the congestion control mechanism of a single TCP flow cannot fully utilize the Gold users' fair share. The small buffer having in a Tofino switch is suboptimal for TCP congestion control. Additionally, we observe that the rate measurement algorithm used in the packet marker could be further refined to enhance TCP performance, which we leave as future work.

By contrast, rate measurement for constant-bitrate UDP traffic is inherently simpler. Our method enables traffic and congestion control-specific loss rates, facilitating the coexistence of different, even incompatible, rate control mechanisms within the same system.

C. Scalability of packet marker

The evaluation scenario shown in Fig. 6 demonstrates how the system scales with a single instance of the SubscriberRate table as presented in Section IV. Note that this table first identifies the user and then updates the user's rate measurement object (implemented as a low-pass filter in Tofino). The results illustrate the average throughput of 35,000 users and the throughput variations within the system. The traffic between TrafficGen-2 and TrafficSink-2 is divided among 7000 Gold users and 28,000 Silver users. The results confirm that the packet marking and CSAQM method effectively maintain the desired resource sharing between the two policy classes, even under such a large-scale user load. The variance of the per user throughput is still limited.

Low-Pass Filter (LPF) objects are expensive resources in the Tofino hardware and the maximum number of LPF cells is approx. 35,800 on a single stage of the Tofino ASIC. We bypassed this limitation by creating multiple instances of the SubscriberRate table and corresponding LPF arrays. We ensured that each instance handles a separate subset of users, distributing user-based rate measurements across multiple stages. Each additional stage dedicated to packet marking expands the capacity by another 35,800 users. This fragmentation of the SubscriberRate table is shown in Fig. 7. To demonstrate this approach, we modified the testbed setup and the pipeline the switch executes to free stage resources for

Fig. 6. 35000 users emulated by 7,000 Gold UDP and 28,000 Silver UDP flows on 100 Gbps bottleneck link

Fig. 7. Multiple instances of the SubscriberRate table needed for scaling up the number of users to be handled.

the multiple table instances. The new pipeline first executes the packet marker method (Fig. 2) with multiple SubscriberRate tables that tags each packet with a packet value. At the end of the pipeline, the switch recirculates the packet and executes the CSAQM packet scheduler algorithm. A bottleneck of 90Gbps is emulated between two ports of the switch. The number of SubscriberRate table instances were limited to six as we needed to place some additional tables for measurements and experiment control.

With this setup, we were able to handle the traffic of 195,000 users. The total aggregated throughput of all users is 100Gbps,

Fig. 8. 195000 users emulated by 39,000 Gold UDP and 156,000 Silver UDP flows on 90 Gbps bottleneck link

generated by TrafficGen-2 on one port. 20 percent of the users (39,000) are Gold and the others (156,000) are Silver. Fig. 8 shows the result of that scenario. We can see each Gold user got 488 Kbps and each Silver approximately 400 Kbps. The throughput of the Silver users is fluctuating, because we are under 1 Mbps and the packet size is 1500 Byte and dropping a packet makes a big impact.

VI. RESOURCE USAGE AND SCALABILITY

The initial implementation of the proposed packet marker method, outlined in Section IV, supports up to 35,800 users while utilizing 5 out of 12 available stages on Tofino hardware. The most resource-intensive component of this implementation is the SubscriberRate table, which consumes SRAM and Map RAM resources to perform user classification and rate measurements based on a Low-Pass Filter (LPF). Despite this complexity, the overall resource consumption remains modest, at 6.1% of SRAM and 6.6% of Map RAM, primarily due to the 66% and 75% utilization in the stage where SubscriberRate and rate measurement operations occur. Seven additional stages remain available in Tofino for other essential network functions, such as forwarding, routing, or User Plane Function (UPF) tasks.

To increase the number of users supported by a single packet marking device, we addressed the 35,800-user limit imposed by the per-stage capacity of LPF objects used for rate measurements. We have shown that by creating multiple instances of the SubscriberRate table and corresponding LPF arrays, we can exceed this limit and distribute user-based rate measurements across multiple stages. Each additional stage dedicated to packet marking expands the capacity by another 35,800 users. With one stage reserved for packet forwarding, the maximum user capacity in a single Tofino pipeline reaches 250,600 (using seven instances of the SubscriberRate table). The overall utilization of mostly used resources still remains modest, at 63.1% of SRAM and 44.1% of Map RAM. Tofino switches have either 2 or 4 pipelines, which run data plane programs independently over different port ranges. One can observe that the number of users to be handled can exceed 1 million when each pipeline is configured to manage the packet tagging of a distinct set of users. Though in this case the whole Tofino device is dedicated for implementing the policy based packet tagging, this process can be done at line-rate and considering the large number of users the per user equipment cost is not significant (around 1 cent).

On Tofino-2 ASICs, where 20 stages are available, a single pipeline can handle up to 537,000 users under the same per-stage constraints. With four pipelines each managing separate user groups, the capacity could potentially surpass 2 million users, significantly enhancing scalability with the proposed packet marking method.

Considering that not all users are active simultaneously and that most traffic is generated by a small subset of users, additional scalability improvements are feasible. A hybrid architecture could offload low-traffic users to a software instance of the packet marking method, while high-throughput users

remain on Tofino hardware. Although software instances can manage a larger number of users, they cannot meet high throughput demands. This approach would require coordination to assign users between hardware and software, potentially boosting overall system scalability. The scheduler has been implemented in P4 for Intel Tofino switches and in C as a Linux kernel module that can be used with the standard tc command. The source codes are publicly available at [8].

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we gave more insight into our CSAQM solution implemented on an Intel Tofino ASIC, where both marking and scheduling algorithms can be run. The key challenge is the marking algorithm implementation because Tofino has some limitations in mathematical calculation and random number generation. We can solve these problems with some per-filled tables. One table stored a binarized function of the TVF. The rates are stored in equal ranges on a logarithmic scale. With this trick we can calculate the value of the continuous function, which is one of the base parts of the PV marking method. The other one stored random rates. The generation of a random number between 0 and the number on Tofino is hard because the device can only generate random values within the range $[0, 2^n - 1]$. With this trick, we can solve these problems too. We presented that this implementation can handle 35,800 subscribers at 100 Gbps bottleneck and 195,000 subscribers at 90 Gbps bottleneck with a single queue, but we gave some hints on how to scale up this to 2 million users.

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